

STRUCTURE OF OXYMETHYLENE METHYL ETHYL KETONE AND OF OXYMETHYLENE METHYL- β -PHENYL ETHYL KETONE.

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By the reaction of self-condensation as also by condensation with cyanoacetamide it is shown that oxymethylene methyl ethyl ketone is $\text{CHOH}=\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)-\text{CO}-\text{CH}_2$ and oxymethylene methyl β -phenyl ethyl ketone is $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-\text{CO}-\text{CH}=\text{CHOH}$. The points of attack of formic ester on the ketone $\text{R}\cdot\text{CH}_2-\text{CO}\cdot\text{CH}_3$ are discussed.

By the action of formic ester on acetone Claisen (*Annalen*, 1894, 281, 309) obtained formyl acetone $\text{CH}_3\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{CHO}$ (I) which according to him exists as the enol oxymethylene acetone $\text{CH}_3\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{CH}=\text{CHOH}$ (II), as it readily undergoes self-condensation to form triacetylbenzene (Claisen and Stylos, *Ber.*, 1888, 21, 1145).

Acetophenone similarly gives oxymethylene acetophenone which by self condensation gives tribenzoyl benzene.

In the case of the unsymmetrical ketone $\text{R}\cdot\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{CH}_3$ (III) formic ester can theoretically react at the methylene or the methyl group each of which is directly linked to the carbonyl and the resulting oxymethylene compound will be either (IV) or (V).

Although oxymethylene compounds have been prepared from some unsymmetrical ketones like (III) we found in the literature evidence which leads to the structure (IV) for some, while (V) for others. Thus Diel and Ilberg (*Ber.*, 1916, 49, 158) prepared the simplest member of the series, oxymethylene methyl ethyl ketone, by Claisen's method as also by the action of formaldehyde in aqueous solution on azobutanone. Since it gives with hydrazine 4:5-dimethylpyrazole they have given the oxymethylene compound the structure (IV, R=Me).

Benary, Meyer and Charisius (*Ber.*, 1926, 59, B, 108, 600) claim that the next homologue oxymethylene methyl propyl ketone is (V, R=Et) since it is transformed by ammonia into 5-butyryl-2-propyl-pyridine.

In view of such observations which indicate that oxymethylene methyl ethyl ketone is (IV, R=Me) but the higher homologue is (V, R=Et) we

thought that it would be of some interest to bring forth some independent evidence bearing on this point. For this purpose we made use of two reactions namely (1) self condensation, such as that shown by oxymethylene acetone and oxymethylene acetophenone, and (2) condensation of these oxymethylene ketones (which are 1 : 3 dicarbonyl compounds and contain therefore a conjugated system) with cyanacetamide.

If a ketone produces the oxymethelene compound (V) three molecules of the latter condense to form the trisubstituted benzene (VI)

If, however, the oxymethylene compound is (IV) self-condensation is not possible. Barat (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 801) condensed oxymethylene acetophenone with cyanoacetamide and obtained 2-hydroxy-6-phenylpyridine. The condensation of cyanacetamide with oxymethylene methyl ethyl ketone, if the latter is (IV, R=Me) should give 2 : 3-dimethyl-5-cyano-6-oxypyridine (VII, R=R₁=Me) which after hydrolysis would yield the acid (VIII, R=R₁=Me). The latter on decarboxylation would give 2 : 3-dimethyl-6-oxypyridine (IX, R=R₁=Me) and finally after reduction 2 : 3-dimethylpyridine (X, R=R₁=Me).

If the oxymethylene compound is (V, R=Et) the final product of condensation with cyanoacetamide will be 2-ethylpyridine (X, R=H; R₁=Et). The final product was confirmed to be 2:3-dimethylpyridine and not its isomer 2-ethylpyridine.

In the matter of self-condensation reaction a striking contrast was observed between oxymethylene methyl ethyl ketone and oxymethylene acetone or oxymethylene acetophenone. The latter in alcoholic solution rapidly undergoes self-condensation and their titre against alkali progressively diminishes due to progressive disappearance of the enol.* Oxymethylene methyl ethyl ketone is a solid, melting at 73°. It could be distilled without decomposition at 250 mm. pressure, and the titre of alkali against a certain volume of its alcoholic solution remained constant over a period of one week. This lack of self-condensation supports the evidence obtained through cyanoacetamide condensation, namely oxymethylene methyl ethyl ketone is (IV, R=Me).

The oxymethylene compound from methyl β-phenylethyl ketone when subjected to the above tests showed an exactly opposite behaviour to that of oxymethylene methyl ethyl ketone. The former, therefore, seems to have the structure (V, R=Ph-CH₂). The titre of alkali required for a certain volume of its alcoholic solution gradually diminished and in the course of a week was roughly reduced to half. Condensation with cyanacetamide, if the oxymethylene compound is represented by (V), should give 2-(β-phenyl ethyl)-5-cyano-6-hydroxypyridine (VII, R=H; R₁=Ph·CH₂·CH₂-) which on hydrolysis should give the acid. The latter on decarboxylation should give 2-(β-phenyl ethyl)-6-hydroxy pyridine (IX, R=H; R₁=Ph·CH₂·CH₂) and finally 2 (β-phenyl ethyl)-pyridine (X, R=H; R₁=Ph·CH₂·CH₂) on reduction. If the oxymethylene ketone is, however, (IV) the final product of cyanoacetamide condensation should be 2-methyl-3-phenyl-methyl pyridine (X, R=PhCH₂; R₁=Me).

As the above two isomeric substituted pyridines have not been synthesised so far independently the proof of the structure of the final product of cyanoacetamide condensation was obtained by its oxidation.

* The reaction of self-condensation of these oxymethylene ketones judged from the alkali titre of the enol as also by estimation of its copper compound is found to be a trimolecular reaction (*unpublished work*).

(X, R=H, R₁=Ph·CH₂·CH₂) should give on oxidation benzoic acid and pyridine- α -carboxylic acid, while (X, R=Ph·CH₂; R₁=Me) should give the $\alpha\beta$ -dicarboxylic acid. Actually benzoic acid and picolinic acid were obtained. The latter, however, could not be isolated and was analysed in the form of its characteristic copper salt.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Oxymethylene methyl ethyl ketone (IV, R=Me) was prepared from methyl ethyl ketone (1 mol.), formic ester (1.5 mol.) and sodium (1 atom) in ether by Claisen's method. It distilled at 105°-110°/250 mm, the distillate solidifying on cooling. The solid melts at 73°.

Condensation of the Oxymethylene ketone with Cyanacetamide. Formation of compound (VII, R=R₁=Me)—Cyanacetamide (11 g.) was dissolved in alcohol (90%) by warming such that it did not separate on cooling. Freshly prepared oxymethylene ketone (19 g.) was added and then finally 8 c.c. of piperidine. The mixture was refluxed on water-bath for 4 hours and the excess of alcohol was distilled off. The residual gum was rubbed with hydrochloric acid and the resulting semi-solid mass when rubbed with acetone became granular, yield 8 g.

It crystallised from alcohol in pale yellow needles, m.p. 270°. (Found: C, 64.6; H, 5.5; N, 19.2. C₈H₈ON₂ requires C, 64.8; H, 5.4; N, 18.9 per cent).

Formation of the Acid (VIII, R=R₁=Me).—The above cyano compound (5 g.) was heated in oil-bath at 150° for 2 hours with 30 c.c. of 50% sulphuric acid. The liquid on cooling was poured into water and the yellowish solid which separated was filtered, washed and dried. It was crystallised from glacial acetic acid in plates, which did not melt even up to 280°, yield almost theoretical. [Found: C, 57.5; H, 5.4; N, 8.2; Equiv., 166 (monobasic). C₈H₈O₂N requires C, 57.49; H, 5.38; N, 8.38 per cent. Equiv., 167).

Decarboxylation of the Acid (VIII, R=R₁=Me): Formation of the hydroxy pyridine (IX, R=R₁=Me). The above acid (4 g.), mixed with a little copper powder, was distilled and the distillate solidified and weighed about 3 g. If crystallised from pyridine, m.p. 205°. (Found: C, 68.8; H, 7.2; N, 11.6. C₇H₈ON requires C, 68.3; H, 7.3; N, 11.4 per cent).

Reduction of the Hydroxy pyridine to 2:3-Dimethylpyridine.—The oxypyridine (IX, R=R₁=Me) (5.5 g.) was mixed with zinc dust (110 g.) and distilled in a current of dry hydrogen from a glass tube drawn out at

one end and heated in a small furnace. A yellowish liquid (3 g.) with pyridine-like odour was collected. This distilled at $160-61^{\circ}/710$ mm. (Found: N, 12.7. C_7H_9N requires N, 13.1 per cent). The picrate melts at 181° and the chloroplatinate at 216° (decomp.). [Found: Pt, 31.06. $(C_7H_9N)_2PtCl_4H_2$ requires Pt, 31.25 per cent]. 2:3-Dimethylpyridine boils at $163-64^{\circ}/760$ mm. Its picrate and the chloroplatinate melt at 83° and 216° respectively. 2-Ethyl pyridine boils at $148-50^{\circ}/760$ mm. and its picrate and the chloroplatinate melt at $187-89^{\circ}$ and $165-67^{\circ}$ respectively. The identity of the base with 2:3-dimethyl pyridine was finally established by permanganate oxidation of the base to quinolinic acid whose melting point and the mixed melting point with a genuine specimen of quinolinic acid obtained from quinoline by oxidation was found to be 180° .

Oxymethylene Methyl- β -phenylethyl Ketone (V, R = $PhCH_2$) was prepared from benzylacetone, formic ester and sodium by Claisen's method. Benzylacetone was obtained from benzal acetone by reduction by sodium amalgam. Benzylacetone (10 g.) yielded about 11 g. of the crude oxymethylene ketone as a liquid. The latter distilled at $110-11^{\circ}/3$ mm. as a lemon-yellow liquid which solidified on colling. The oxymethylene ketone colours ferric chloride red and forms a copper salt which was crystallised from alcohol in plates, m.p. 176° (decomp.).

[Found: Cu, 15.7 $(C_{11}H_{11}O_2)_2Cu$ requires Cu, 15.35 per cent]. Its anilide melts at 132° . (Found: N, 6.0. $C_{17}H_{17}ON$ requires N, 5.6 per cent).

The oxymethylene ketone began to change from light yellow to deep red and, due to the chemical change it was undergoing, it could not be purified. The titre of alkali against a certain volume of its alcoholic solution fell to nearly half during the course of one week.

Condensation of the Oxymethylene Ketone with Cyanoacetamide. Formation of 2- β -Phenylethyl -5-cyano-6-hydroxyxyridine (VII, R = H; $R_1 = Ph'CH_2CH_2$).—This was effected as in the case of oxymethylene methyl ethyl ketone. The product was a semi-solid mass which was rubbed with ethyl acetate, filtered and the solid was washed with water to free it from unchanged cyanoacetamide. 10 G. of the oxymethylene ketone yielded about 6 g. of the condensation product. It crystallises from alcohol in clusters of needles, m.p. 198° (decomp.). [Found: C, 74.4; H, 5.2; N, 13.1. $C_{14}H_{13}ON_2$ requires C, 75.0; H, 5.36; N, 12.5 per cent].

On hydrolysis in the manner described under methyl ethyl ketone the above condensation product gave an almost theoretical yield of the carboxylic acid. It crystallised from acetic acid in clusters of needles, m.p. $211-12^{\circ}$. (Found: C, 68.7; H, 5.3; Equiv., 241. $C_{14}H_{13}O_2N$ requires C, 69.1; H, 5.3 per cent. Equiv., 243).

On decarboxylation of the above acid the hydroxy pyridine (IX, R=H; R₁=Ph-CH₂-CH₂) distilled as a liquid which solidified on cooling. The solid crystallised from alcohol as thick small needles, m.p. 152°. (Found: C, 78.1; H, 6.3; N, 7.5. C₁₃H₁₃ON requires C, 78.4; H, 6.5; N, 7.04 per cent).

When distilled with zinc dust in a current of hydrogen the above oxy pyridine gave 2-β-phenylethyl pyridine (X, R=Ph; R₁=Ph-CH₂-CH₂) which was obtained as a liquid with strong pyridine-like odour. It was purified by redistillation. (Found: C, 85.0; H, 7.1; N, 7.6. C₁₃H₁₃N requires C, 85.2; H, 7.1; N, 7.65 per cent).

It forms a chloroplatinate which begins to blacken at 160° and melts at 185°.

Oxidation of 2-β-Phenylethylpyridine.—The base (1.2 g.) was refluxed for 4 hours with a neutral 1.5% solution of potassium permanganate. On filtering, the clear filtrate was concentrated and acidified when a white solid separated. Crystallised from water it melted at 122° and was identified as benzoic acid from its melting point and its equivalent which was found to be 123.

The acid filtrate from benzoic acid was made exactly neutral by adding alkali and again concentrated. On adding cold concentrated solution of copper acetate the copper salt of picolinic acid came out as a shining blue crystalline solid. It was filtered, washed with water, dried, and analysed [Found: Cu, 18.6. Calc. for (C₆H₄O₂N)₂Cu + 2H₂O : Cu, 18.6 per cent].